

Annotation Methodology Technical Report

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Background

The original motivation for this work was to support the United States Social Security Administration (SSA) to improve their disability determination process. Our aim was to develop clinical natural language processing (NLP) tools that SSA adjudicators could use to quickly extract activity functioning information in the health records collected as part of work disability claims (Marfeo et al., 2025; Zirikly et al., 2022). By facilitating quick access to activity functioning information, the disability determination process has potential to be more timely, accurate and efficient and reduce the wait times for benefit decisions (Goldman et al., 2023).

Activity functioning refers to the tasks of everyday life that occupy one's time. These activities are what one wants to do, has to do, or is expected to do within one's social roles and contextual situations. Activity functioning is recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO) as an outcome of how an individual experiences their health (World Health Organization, 2001). Activity functioning information in health records is a data source that, when extracted and measured, can be used to determine health outcomes, inform health policy and resource allocation, and in the context of this work, inform disability and every-day activity functional status.

This report outlines and describes in detail the methodology applied in the manual annotation process to identify and code activity functioning information in clinical records. The manual annotation methodology described in this report has been the basis upon which (manual) [annotation guidelines for activity domains](#) were developed (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d) with the goal of developing a gold standard corpus for evaluating and training computer models for each activity domain. This work has led to the development of NLP tools that automate the extraction of activity functioning information in health records.

This document provides a roadmap for the manual annotation process in clinical notes that others can follow. When we first began this work, no detailed roadmap existed, and the methods described here were created over time organically, sometimes with trial and error. As our work progressed, we relied on previous methods we had created that streamlined our annotation work (Thieu et al., 2017; Thieu et al., 2021) and oriented us as to what stage we were in and tasks we needed to accomplish. It is our hope that others involved in manual annotation work will find this document useful.

Data Sources

Data used for manual annotation were obtained from two sources: (1) clinical notes provided by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Biomedical Translational Research information system (BTRIS), and (2) medical records collected by SSA for adjudicating work disability claims. Clinical notes from NIH included a broad range of documentation such as neuropsychological assessments; therapy notes from physical, occupational, speech-language, and recreational therapists; vocational rehabilitation records; and social work

notes. Similarly, documents from SSA comprised various types of medical evidence including consultative examination reports, hospital records (including emergency, inpatient, and outpatient), therapy records, laboratory test results, and progress notes. All medical notes were limited to patients aged 18 or older at the time of the visit. The selection of these notes was detailed in the individual annotation guidelines (cite website). For a comprehensive description of the datasets (including clinical notes and medical records) used for each activity domain, please refer to the publication titled [*Applying NLP methods to code functional performance in electronic health records using the international classification of functioning, disability, and health*](#) (Marfeo et al., 2025). The following sections describe the main stages of manual annotation we identified: Preparatory, Exploratory, Pre-annotation, Independent annotation, and the Gold Standard Corpus stage. These stages of the annotation process are outlined and further described below.

Preparatory Stage

Selection of a conceptual framework

We used the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) (World Health Organization, 2001) as a framework to conceptualize functioning and standardize annotation of information at the activities level in electronic health records. The ICF was selected in view of its classification taxonomy of human functioning that has world-wide adoption and provides standardized language of functioning concepts with codes and operational definitions. By establishing a common language for describing health and health-related states, the ICF has potential to improve communication between users, permit comparison of data across countries and disciplines, and provide a systematic coding scheme to be used by health information systems.

The ICF conceptualizes activity functioning from other types of functioning such as body functions. Body function information was already being captured as part of the SSA business process. However, body function information may or may not impact activity functioning. By including activity functioning information, a more complete picture of a person's functioning can be discerned and a more accurate assessment of work disability made. For example, a body structure loss of the little and ring fingers on a dominant hand can limit hand function and only be a slight impairment to function in a role as teacher, yet a major impairment if one's livelihood was as a concert pianist.

The ICF provides a taxonomy of human functioning with the Activities and Participation component as the central outcome of health. See Figure 1 that depicts the ICF schema (World Health Organization, 2001). Functioning is classified on multiple levels from body structures (e.g., cellular, or organ, or organ system configurations); to body functions (e.g., mental functions); and functioning at the level of activities and participation of the person (e.g., self-care activities or work participation). An individual's functioning in a specific activity domain is understood as a complex relationship with dynamic interaction among a

person's health condition, body structures and functions, and personal and environmental contextual factors (World Health Organization, 2001). Disability is understood as activity limitations or participation restrictions resulting from impairments and/or environmental barriers. See Figure 1, the ICF scheme with the activity component highlighted, to show the focus of this work is on activity functioning.

Figure 1. ICF framework with the Activity component highlighted

The Activities and Participation component of the ICF is made up of nine life area domains (See Figure 2). We determined seven of these domains as activity domains and two as participation domains. As our focus was on activity functioning, and not participation, the seven domains we selected for annotation and their corresponding ICF chapter codes were (d1) Learning and Applying Knowledge; (d2) General Tasks and Demands; (d3) Communication; (d4) Mobility; (d5) Self-care; (d6) Domestic Life, and (d7) Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships. Within each of these activity domains, the ICF provides more detailed classification of activity concepts and codes.

Figure 2. ICF Activities and Participation component with life area domains

Selection and Training of Annotators

Over the period of this project, the annotators were a team of six people, with 2-5 persons at any one time working on the project. They ranged in age from 33 to 76 years of age and included four females and two males. Socioeconomically, they came from the middle and upper-middle income classes. Regarding first language, three annotators had English as their first language, one had Chinese and two had Spanish. Proficiency in the language of the data being annotated (English) was native for three of the annotators and bilingual for the other three. Members of the annotation team were deliberately selected for their diverse backgrounds, clinical expertise, and understanding of clinical language used to document functional domains of interest. The annotation team included clinical rehabilitation domain experts with backgrounds in medicine, occupational therapy, physical therapy, and individuals with public health and data science expertise.

Annotator training was overseen by one of the two original human annotators that had annotated the Mobility domain and developed a Mobility Gold Standard Corpus. Training of new annotators began by orientation to the phenomenon of “annotation”, an overview of the SSA project and how the process of annotation fit within this context. The GATE software tool was introduced, and the annotator trainee became familiar with using GATE. A practice set of 6 NIH-BTRIS clinical document files were annotated for mobility and compared to the Mobility GSC. Discrepancy analysis between the trainee’s annotations and the Mobility GSC was run, and these were discussed line by line for the rationale of

how they had been annotated according to the GSC. After completion of one practice set with discussion of discrepancies, the trainee was provided with 10 NIH-BTRIS files to annotate as an IRR set. We used entity micro level F1-scores and Token micro level F1-scores to determine IRR. If scores were satisfactory, the trainee was cleared to begin independent annotations for the Mobility domain.

Selection of an Annotation tool

We conducted an exploration of annotation tools at the beginning of the project. The criteria for consideration were the ease of use and features that support documents in multiple formats, such as XML, HTML, and plain text. The General Architecture for Text Engineering (GATE) annotation software tool (Cunningham et al., 2011) was selected for its versatility and user-friendliness as well as the ability to customize annotation schemas for the identification of functioning mentions, including additional attributes and values that could more accurately represent these mentions.

Deciding on sequence of activity domains for annotation

As this work was novel, we relied upon clinical expertise to decide upon which activity domain to begin annotation. We decided to grade our approach from simple to complex, beginning with an activity domain that would likely be more straightforward in functional descriptions, and then advance to those domains that could have greater complexity. Mobility, ICF Chapter d4, was selected as the first ICF domain to be annotated, as we predicted the clinical language and ICF mobility codes to be more straightforward. Self-care and Domestic Life, ICF Chapters d5 and d6 were the next two ICF domains annotated and were combined for annotation purposes, as functional descriptors were similar in language for personal and instrumental activities of daily living. The ICF domain of Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (ICF chapter d7) was annotated next. Finally, the ICF domains for Communication and Cognition, specifically, chapters d1 Learning and Applying Knowledge, d2 General Tasks and Demands, and d3 Communication, were combined into a single domain labeled as ComCog for our purposes. These activity domains have been found to factor together closely in prior work (Jette et al., 2019) and were the most complex to annotate.

Exploratory Stage

This stage of the annotation process represents work designed to see how well the ICF framework and codes represent information about a person's functional performance in the activity domains, as documented in clinical text; to begin to create and test annotation schemas to capture this information; and to begin to develop annotation guidelines.

Exploring clinical documentation for activity domain information

The exploratory phase was undertaken to familiarize annotators with domain specific information in clinical documentation and determine the type of clinical notes to be selected for annotation. The process began by selecting an activity domain in the ICF (e.g., mobility), and based upon domain expertise, identifying the specific types of clinical notes likely to contain the most relevant information for a particular activity domain. Annotators reviewed a subset of clinical records written by providers deemed likely to have domain expertise and document functional information related to the specific activity domain of interest.

Clinical note types used for exploratory analysis came from the following disciplines: neuropsychology, occupational and physical therapy, speech and language pathology, social work, and recreational and vocational therapy. For further data information, please refer to the respective activity annotation guidelines for [Mobility](#), [Self-Care & Domestic Life](#); [Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships](#); and [Communication & Cognition](#).

Developing and testing the annotation schema

For each activity domain, an exploratory annotation schema was developed based on the ICF framework, which was used to label information of interest in clinical notes. Using a small subset of notes, annotators independently annotated the same files using the exploratory schema. Discrepancy analyses were performed and used for discussion among annotators to reach consensus and further refine the schema and determine how well the ICF codes represent the clinical documentation of domain-specific functioning information. Testing the schema continued through an iterative process of reviewing subsets of the data until annotators agreed that the schema and coding structure allowed for the full capture of domain-specific functional information.

Annotation schemas covered a range of information such as timeline, source of information, level of functional limitations, and type of required assistance. Please refer to the annotation schemas for each of the four activity domains developed for Mobility, SCDL, IPIR, and ComCog.

Developing and refining the annotation guidelines

Annotation guidelines that documented general and specific principles and examples of annotation for each activity domain were developed simultaneously with the relevant schema. The content of each guideline included an introduction that operationally defined the domain of interest, a section on data selection and methods, an extensive section on the annotation schema with all entities, attributes and values defined, and a section on the software tool selected and used for annotation. Text examples from clinical notes that

represented the respective schemas for each domain were provided to illustrate what to annotate, what not to annotate, and the reasons why. Annotation guidelines were updated and repopulated with text examples as needed to decipher difficult to determine annotations using an iterative process involving discussions to obtain consensus among annotators.

Pre-annotation Stage

The pre-annotation stage is an iterative process that involves refining the annotation schema, annotation guideline and in some instances refining the sampling process.

Determining the Annotation Schema

Based upon previous exploratory work, annotation schemas for each domain were finalized. The annotation schemas for the activity domains of Mobility, SCDL, and ComCog were similar in that they required annotators to select a span of text to annotate the domain entity. This was unlike the IPIR schema that was used on datasets that had been pre-processed with sentence segments. All annotation schemas were organized hierarchically with the main conceptual component as the upper-level entity, followed by sub-entities, attributes, and values.

Establishing inter-rater reliability (IRR)

To enhance reliability of annotations for each domain, annotators applied both the relevant schema and guideline to conduct a series of exploratory annotations using the same new dataset of clinical documents (see IRR data tables). Results of exploratory annotations were evaluated for quality assurance and discrepancy analysis among annotators. This process was repeated among annotators until ambiguous, unique, or challenging cases reached a consensus and were therefore resolved. The annotators also sought input from domain content experts for challenging cases during the process. The guideline was updated with a refined schema and new information as it was found.

Through this iterative process of reviewing annotated subsets of the data, the annotation guidelines and schemas were refined and updated until both were sufficiently clear to allow reproduceable, consistent annotations so that annotators could perform individual annotations. The acceptable level of inter-rater reliability (IRR) was established a priori at 0.80. For difficult annotation tasks, the IRR threshold could be as low as 0.70. IRR was established with at least two to three persons for each of the four activity domains. Independent (individual) annotations followed after a satisfactory IRR was reached for each domain.

Independent Annotation Stage

Upon completing the pre-annotation stage with satisfactory IRR results, the annotators independently annotated their assigned corpora, which included selected clinical notes for each activity domain. Given the large volume of notes to be annotated, we encountered previously unseen cases that posed annotation challenges and required additional clarification to ensure accuracy and consistency. Additional discussions were held among annotators to address these cases and reach consensus.

Developing and Publishing the Gold Standard Corpus

Based on finalized annotated corpora, we constructed a benchmark corpus (i.e., gold standard corpus (GSC)) for evaluating and training models for each activity domain.

After each activity domain was established, a single corpus containing annotations for all four domains was developed. The Gold Standard Corpus for Activity Functioning Information (GoSCAI) version 1.0 (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025e) was published on Zenodo in May, 2025. This dataset was curated for the purpose of training natural language processing models to automatically identify, extract, and classify information on human functioning at the whole-person, or activity, level.

Conclusion

Our intention for this report was to outline the methodology process we used to standardize manual annotations of activity functioning information in clinical records. This is an essential first step in the NLP process that relies on standardized manual annotations to construct automated NLP extraction tools. Though the manual annotation process described here was specific to activity functioning information, its application could be broadened to other types of textual information.

We have published manual annotation guidelines version 1.0 on Zenodo in 2024 and updated these annotation guidelines for [Mobility](#), [Self-Care & Domestic Life](#), [Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships](#), and [Communication & Cognition](#) to version 1.1 in 2025. The guidelines explain the importance of functioning information for each activity domain and provide a detailed roadmap of the manual annotation process that others may find useful to follow.

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